

Scientific Considerations to Move Towards Biowaiver for BCS Class III Drugs: How Modeling and Simulation Can Help?

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1. Need and challenges of using model based BCS III waiver

In December 2017, U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) issued the Guidance for Industry; Waiver of In Vivo Bioavailability and Bioequivalence (BE) Studies for Immediate Release Solid Oral Dosage Forms Based on a Biopharmaceutical Classification System (BCS) (1). Per this guidance, to qualify for a BCS-based biowaiver, the following criteria should be demonstrated for BCS Class III drug products:

- a) the drug substance is highly soluble,
- b) the drug products (test and reference) are very rapidly dissolving (>85% in 15 min across physiological pH range), and
- c) the test (T) product and reference listed drug (RLD) formulations are qualitatively the same and quantitatively very similar.

These criteria were ratified by the International Council for Harmonization (ICH) M9 guideline endorsed in June 2018. In addition to the general guidance, product specific guidances issued by the FDA echoed the same verbiage and regulatory criteria when referring to BCS-based biowaiver option for class III drugs (highly soluble but poorly permeable). For rapidly dissolving dosage forms containing BCS class III drugs, intestinal permeability is the major rate-limiting step in oral drug absorption. Provided that excipients do not affect intestinal drug permeability, absorption rate would be controlled by drug-specific properties and physiological factors rather than formulation-related variables (2). Therefore, current regulatory policies on waiving *in vivo* BE studies for immediate release dosage form require that T and RLD formulations be qualitatively the same (Q1) and quantitatively very similar (Q2), which will be referred to as the Q1/Q2 recommendation in this article.

The Q1/Q2 recommendations for BCS III waiver can become challenging under special circumstances due to patent protection, manufacturing need, and development cost. Advance in technology and quantitative modeling and simulation can provide an effective means to evaluate and mitigate risks associated with non Q1/Q2 formulations. It is of great importance to systematically characterize potential excipient effects on intestinal drug permeability and transporter, which have been studied in FDA sponsored research.

Overall, *in vitro-in vivo* correlations (IVIVC) using conventional mass balance deconvolution approaches assuming a single absorption compartment, Wagner-Nelson or Loo-Riegelman methods, are not expected for very rapidly dissolving dosage forms containing BCS III drugs (2, 3). The reason for this discrepancy is in a key underlying assumption required to apply deconvolution, *i.e.*, the unknown input and unit impulse response enter the system in the same location. In case of compounds which are not highly permeable, absorption is not confined to a short segment of the gut. The dissolved fraction may transit to a location different to that where dissolution occurs before entering the systemic circulation (3) and the heterogeneity of small intestine, in terms of enzyme expression and enteric metabolism (4) and regional intestinal effective permeability (5, 6), should be taken into account when estimating the fraction absorbed.

Since conventional mass balance deconvolution techniques are not able to disentangle different kinetic processes contributing to the input function, *e.g.*, dissolution, gastrointestinal transit and permeation, they measure the *in vivo* fraction absorbed, not the fraction dissolved. In this context, advances in establishing physiologically-based IVIVC using variants of the compartmental absorption and transit model, which extends the mixing tank model to characterize drug transit through the gastrointestinal tract, may support biowaiver for Q1/Q2 formulations containing BCS III drugs, but not showing very rapid dissolution *in vitro*. However, knowledge gaps still need to be closed to enable the envisioned pathway to combine *in vitro* testing and physiologically based modeling as a promising biowaiver practice.

2. Current scientific considerations for supporting BCS III drug waiver and modeling BCS III drug absorption

One of the biggest challenges in linking the *in vitro* performance of a formulation (mainly disintegration and dissolution) and the *in vivo* behavior in gastrointestinal tract, is the fact that typical clinical data do not involve direct measures of behavior within stomach or gut lumen. Since assessing *in vivo* dissolution is challenging and impractical outside specific research settings (7), investigators rely on establishing correlations between the *in vivo* performance and some attributes of the observed or estimated pharmacokinetics (so-called IVIVC). As mentioned above for poorly permeable drugs, the conventional IVIVC may become highly non-linear. Philosophically there have been two camps on how to resolve the issue. In one side people have been trying to modify the *in vitro* testing systems and bring what they have coined as “*in vivo* predictive dissolution tests” via various modifications to the testing system to mimic some aspects of the physiology (see Misra et al (8) for a recent review). However, others have been promoting incorporation of the gastrointestinal system attributes into the physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models such that disproportionate changes in features of concentration time profile with changes in dissolution could be defined (9).

The advantage of the former approach is its simplicity once established. However, establishing the “*in vivo* predictive dissolution” is not an easy task and more over one predictive system for a certain drug and formulation may not be predictive for another drug and formulation, hence reducing the possibility of generalization.

The second philosophy involves the utilization of mechanistic gastrointestinal tract model to generate IVIVC. Even though promising, this approach is rather challenging, requiring PBPK expertise and specialized software/models. Disassembling *in vitro* data into their major mechanistic constituents (to link the release with shear stress, pH, buffer capacity, fluid volume and so on) followed by subsequent reassembly within PBPK models have allowed researchers to prospect drug release variability at the absorbing site. In the case of oral drug absorption, modeling *in vitro* dissolution profiles, rather than directly inputting experimental dissolution data (tabulated % dissolved vs time), allows the combination of drug- (*e.g.*, solubility and bile micelle:water partition coefficient) and formulation-specific properties (*e.g.*, product-specific particle size distribution) with gastrointestinal variability (*e.g.*, intraluminal pH, intestinal fluid

volume and bile salts concentration), generating intraluminal dissolution profiles for different individuals (10-12).

Significant efforts have been made to characterize interindividual (between subjects) variability in the gastrointestinal tract (13), however, intraindividual (within subject) variability is much less understood. Moreover, there is a long standing debate on distinguishing the discrepancies between true intraindividual variability and Interoccasion variability (14-17). The latter encompass both natural / periodic variations in physiology and biology of the body as well as the changes that occur in the system due to two occasions of the experiments not being fully controlled and similar. Although, ideally controlled studies should minimize this, some elements cannot be exactly the same in any clinical setting (such as variable anxiety level due to sequence effect). Therefore, in the realm of bioequivalence (BE) studies, balancing the study design is essential. Even with such balance, e.g., using cross-over study design, a high intraindividual variability may confound the results of a BE evaluation. In other words, the average value of relative bioavailability can be protected through the cross-over design, however, overlooking the intraindividual variability may fail to capture the true confidence interval around the mean. Thus, to prevent any crossover virtual bioequivalence trials (VBE) becoming associated with false positive or false negative results (compared to any real large scale BE results), it is crucial to inform the models with correct estimates of within subject variability(11). Furthermore, this iterative modeling workflow can accommodate the IVIVC for various in vivo conditions (patients vs healthy subjects, stratified populations, etc.) without changing the in the dissolution methodology (10, 12, 18-20).

VBE models can also be used to explore various hypothetical or anecdotal inter-correlations between model parameters and compare them with observed BE studies for consistency(21, 22). The conventional sensitivity analysis is muddled by the fact that the majority of users look into changing one parameter at a time and assuming that the rest of the parameters remain unchanged. These assumptions have been challenged recently by indication of many inter-correlations between physiological parameters (21, 22). Although the publications have not been focusing on the gastrointestinal physiology, such inter-correlations are also expected in the intestinal lumen.

2.1 GI physiology related to absorption of BCS III drugs including permeation, e.g., transporters

Bioavailability (and hence BE) of many drug products may depend on the interplay of the formulation and drug with enzymes and transporters in gut wall. CYP3A and P-glycoprotein are present at high levels in the villous tip of enterocytes in the small intestine. In addition to CYP enzymes, UDP-glucuronosyltransferases, sulfotransferases and glutathione S-transferases are present in the small intestine. There are also several transporters located in the apical and basolateral membrane possessing influx or efflux functions. The progress in LCMS-based proteomics field over the last decade has helped with better characterization of the drug metabolizing enzymes and transporters (23). The possibility of quantitative extrapolation of metabolism and transporter information from in vitro to in vivo systems through the LCMS techniques for proteomics has been the major motivation behind the recent surge in the use of

various microphysiological systems (organ-on-chip). The intestinal epithelium is a highly dynamic environment because of continuous exposure to high concentrations of inducers (ingested compounds) and the short life span of enterocytes (24). It is important to realize that the distribution of the enzymes and transporters alongside the gut wall is not uniform. Since BCS III drugs may show segmental dependent permeability through the gut, changes in dissolution rate may affect the interaction of the drug with the enzymes and transporters disproportionately. Such scenarios have been the subject of several studies to assess the interplay between the formulation/enzyme and transporters (25) and the impact on bioavailability of parent vs metabolites (26, 27).

2.2 Formulation and its impact on permeation

Currently, there is an emerging body of evidence assessing the impact of excipients on the apparent permeability of drugs across *in vitro* monolayer models (e.g., Caco-2 and MDCK cell lines) and *in situ* rat intestinal perfusion models. For example, hydroxypropylmethylcellulose, povidone, polyethylene glycol 400, sodium lauryl sulfate, and lactose within tested concentration ranges did not affect the permeability of the selected BCS III drugs (28). On the other hand, Rege and co-workers reported that some surfactants, including sodium lauryl sulfate, significantly increased the apical-to-basolateral permeability of furosemide, cimetidine, and hydrochlorotiazide presumably by inhibiting their active efflux, since mannitol permeability, a paracellular transport marker, was not affected (29). The *in vivo* consequences of these observations from preclinical models are largely unknown. However, *in vitro-in vivo* extrapolation may help to simulate various scenarios and assess their compatibility with sparse observations when there are no direct clinical studies.

The approval via *in vivo* BE studies of multiple generics containing BCS III drugs and formulated distinctly from the respective reference drug products empirically advocates a minor impact of commonly used excipients on intestinal permeability (30). Nevertheless, the lack of evidence of excipients affecting oral absorption of BCS III drugs is not a concrete evidence of the absence of such an effect. To further understand the impact of excipients on BE, the Office of Generic Drugs (OGD) has been conducting internal analyses on *in vivo* BE studies, formulations, and dissolution data of both RLD and generic products. External research studies have been awarded to screen approved excipients in the USA and investigate their potential impacts on permeability and intestinal transporters (31). For example, through 3 four-way crossover BE studies, 12 common excipients at large amounts were found to not impact the absorption of two BCS class III representatives in humans. On the other hand, two commonly used excipients, namely hydroxypropylmethylcellulose and microcrystalline cellulose significantly affected systemic drug exposure (32). Overall, the goal of these research projects is to identify a list of excipients that may potentially affect solubility, permeability, and transporter and enzyme activities as well as to identify the safe range of excipients for a list of drugs for which systemic exposure is less likely to be affected. For example, one of the Generic Drug User Fee Amendment (GDUFA) funded contract is “*expanding BCS class III waivers for generic drugs to non- qualitatively*

(Q1)/quantitatively (Q2)". The outcome of these research studies may serve as the scientific basis for improving confidence in the use of varying amounts of excipients and potentially expand BCS Class III waivers for generic drugs to non-Q1/Q2 formulations.

Cimetidine and acyclovir were the model drugs selected for the clinical studies quantitatively investigating the impact of excipients on the absorption of not highly permeable drugs. Cimetidine is a weak substrate of efflux transporters and also a substrate for the organic anion transporter 3 (OAT3) (33, 34). Acyclovir uptake seems to be mediated by OAT1 (33). It is possible that other BCS III drugs have properties that differ from cimetidine and acyclovir to render those drugs susceptible to other excipient influences that cause modified drug absorption (32). However, as permutations of various BCS III drugs (e.g., substrates of different uptake and efflux transporters) and excipients are almost endless, it would be highly impractical to carry out *in vivo* BE studies exploring the entire range of potential combinations. An attractive and efficient alternative would be to assess these permutations in physiologically-relevant *in vitro* systems with subsequent translation of the data into systemic exposure using quantitative methods and modeling.

Current *in vitro* monolayer models used to assess apparent drug permeability are based on cell lines, e.g., Caco-2 monolayer culture, that were originally isolated from tumor samples and they harbor multiple gene mutations. However, this *in vitro* evaluation system does not always recapitulate the complexity the small intestine microenvironment. For example, the lack of tissue-specific architecture, cell-cell and cell-matrix interactions, especially the lack of cytochrome P450 enzymes and membrane transporter expression, may reduce the biorelevance of the *in vitro* systems for evaluating the impact of excipients on the permeability of some drugs with transporter-mediated absorption (35, 36). Since intestinal permeability of BCS III drugs may be dependent on transporter-mediated kinetics or on the enzyme-transporter interplay, improving the biorelevance of the *in vitro* system is needed. Recently, digesting biopsy- or human pluripotent stem cell-derived enteroids and seeding them onto microdevices has been demonstrated to recapitulate the transcriptomic and architecture of human small intestine (36-38). Future studies are still needed to assess whether such microphysiological systems can predict drug absorption across enterocytes on a standalone basis as well as when integrated to PBPK models leveraging the state-of-art knowledge on intestinal membrane transporters (39-41).

2.3 Conducting VBE using PBPK for BCS class III drugs and potential regulatory impact

The rate and extent of oral absorption in the intestine, especially for immediate release dosage forms, are governed by three major factors other than physiological factors: rate of *in vivo* dissolution, solubility, and permeability across the intestinal membrane (42). The level of excipients in the gut lumen and enterocyte may dictate the magnitude of changes (e.g., on solubility, permeability, increase or decrease of the function of transporters, and/or enzyme functions) in oral drug absorption. In addition to GDUFA supported research on screening the approved excipients in the USA and their potential impact on permeability and intestinal transporters, scientists in OGD also applied PBPK modeling approach to investigate the general impact of excipients on oral drug absorption and their risks in the context of bioequivalence (43). The main purpose of this PBPK practice is more to provide a methodology and risk assessment

tool for identifying potential BE risks rather than providing a definite answer for specific drugs. The simulation results showed that changes in solubility had minimal impact on C_{\max} and AUC_{0-t} of investigated BCS class I and III drugs. Changes in passive permeability altered C_{\max} more than AUC_{0-t} for BCS class I drugs but were variable and drug-specific across different BCS class II and III drugs. Reducing or increasing influx and efflux transporter activity might likely affect C_{\max} and AUC_{0-t} of BCS class II and III drugs, but the magnitude may be drug dependent. Changes in passive permeability and/or transporter activity for BCS class II and III drugs might also have a significant impact on fraction absorbed and systemic bioavailability while changes in intestinal metabolic activity may have an impact on gut and systemic bioavailability. This project demonstrated the potential capability of PBPK model to ascertain the potential impact of excipients on drug absorption and bioavailability.

The recently published papers also demonstrated the utility of PBPK absorption modeling and simulation to support the pharmacokinetic evaluation for BCS Class III Drugs (44, 45). A PBPK models for a BCS class III drug, saxagliptin has been developed and optimized after optimization of permeability and intersystem extrapolation factor (ISEF). Sensitivity analysis on absorption-related parameters suggested that permeability and ISEF has a significant impact on extent of drug exposure in comparison to other factors (e.g., particle size, precipitation rate). The verified model was used to demonstrate the lack of effects of acid reducing agents on the drug exposure of saxagliptin (44). In the other study (45), PBPK model was developed for a putative BCS Class I/III drug, oseltamivir phosphate and its metabolite oseltamivir carboxylate in both adults and pediatrics. Virtual BE simulations were conducted to establish BE dissolution safe space for oseltamivir phosphate in both adults and pediatrics. The virtual BE analysis indicated that drug products with the dissolution boundary at 10% slower than dissolution profile of pivotal bio-batch could maintain BE to RLD in adults. In contrast, a stringent trend of dissolution boundary (safe space) was observed for pediatrics (6% slower for 8-18-year-old adolescents, 4% slower for neonates). This study highlights the utility of physiology-based absorption modeling to inform virtual BE trial, providing a quantitative basis for setting clinically relevant specifications for dissolution for oseltamivir phosphate in both adults and pediatric populations. These modeling exercises indicated that PBPK-based virtual BE trials could be used as an alternative to *in vivo* BE studies, informing and modernizing regulatory decision making in the realm of generic drugs.

2.4 Current process and thoughts on incorporating the inter- and intraindividual variabilities in PBPK model

For virtual BE simulations, variability inputs play an important role. Variability is different from uncertainty, although their effects may be confounded and mingled. Uncertainty (“noise”) can be either qualitative (i.e., lack of knowledge) or quantitative (i.e., emerging from non-precise measurement methods). Furthermore, studying a limited population sample introduces an element of randomness when attempting to extrapolate the results to the whole population. Uncertainty can be mitigated or even eliminated with more or better data whereas variability by its nature is irreducible. Variability refers to the inherent heterogeneity or diversity of data in an assessment and can only be better characterized. Disentangling uncertainty and variability has

been addressed by two major, complementary, modeling approaches: *a priori* and *a posteriori* modelling (46).

Individual differences in systemic exposure and its impact on dose requirements is of relevance to clinicians as well as scientists working in drug development. Understanding the mechanisms by which intrinsic and extrinsic factors affect drug exposure provides the opportunity to pre-select covariates and optimize drug posology. First attempts to quantify determinants of drug concentration in a population of patients led to population pharmacokinetic models (47). Overall, such *a posteriori* modeling of interindividual variability, also referred to as top-down approach, is data-driven and based on non-linear mixed effects modeling of population data sets in the health sciences. After unveiling the determinants of variability, population pharmacokinetics models can be used to run prospective simulations to assess their impact in various clinically relevant but yet untested scenarios. Population pharmacokinetics has been extensively reviewed elsewhere (48, 49), and is out of the scope of this research.

A priori modeling of variability can be undertaken by combining deterministic descriptions of the determinants of variability and stochastic simulations, acknowledging that part of the interindividual variability may occur by chance. Under the overarching umbrella of model informed drug discovery and development, PBPK modeling has played an important role in assessing *a priori* sources of variability. Conceptually, the utilization of drug-specific parameters distinguishes PBPK models from classical descriptive models of observed data using purely statistical/mathematical models (50). Most of these parameters are usually, but not exclusively, measured *in vitro*. Translation of these values within PBPK models requires combination with system components. For example, the fraction unbound in plasma (f_u) depends on the drug affinity to human serum albumin as well as on the individual's albumin level in plasma. PBPK models can be parametrized to either directly use f_u , as a single inputted value, or dynamically determine f_u based on the albumin level and the drug affinity to albumin. Even though the PBPK model structure in both approaches is the same, the latter incorporates the covariates influencing albumin levels, which in turn enables predicting the related interindividual variability (51, 52). Therefore, it is imperative to mechanistically incorporate covariates in these models and employ correlated Monte Carlo simulations to interrogate clinically-derived probability distributions of system parameters and generate anatomically and physiologically realistic virtual subjects.

Incorporation of stochastic variability in model parameters can be challenging due to the physiological constraints that may arise. During the development of mechanistic population PBPK models, certain physiological constraints do not apply independently on model parameters, but on their joint population distribution. Therefore, a biased/misplaced stochastic model may lead to incorrect variance structure (53). The basic assumption made by Monte Carlo simulations is that the randomness of the dependent variable is simply due to the randomness in independent variables. In this context, a virtual subject would be defined by randomly selecting anatomy- and physiology-related parameters from probability distributions computed directly from clinical observations. The caveat of this approach is the generation of anatomically and/or physiologically unrealistic virtual individuals and populations. Therefore, correlated Monte Carlo methods are

needed. Overall, the system parameters are scaled using a hierarchical structure, which considers the covariance matrix dictating parameter's interdependencies. For example, the randomly assigned age and gender of a virtual individual selected from an age–gender distribution will dictate the position of that individual on the probability distribution of subsequent correlated parameters (e.g., body weight, organ volume, etc.) (52).

There are two ways how intraindividual variability can be incorporated into the PBPK-based VBE trials. The first option is to simply attribute intraindividual variability obtained from a previous replicated clinical study to the predicted BE metrics *post hoc*. This is a pragmatic approach that lacks mechanistic understanding of changes in system components between two different occasions. The second option is to include the intraindividual variability in the system parameters and propagate it through simulations (54). In one of the recent examples of VBE with naproxen where intraindividual variability was propagated through simulations, its value was arbitrarily chosen to be 30% and it was added to selected gastrointestinal parameters, e.g., mean gastric emptying time, gastric and intestinal pH and bile salts concentration (11). In that way, predicted variability and derived 90% confidence intervals may get inflated. Alternative approaches have been suggested to overcome the limitations related to the poor understanding of the sources of intraindividual variability in systemic drug exposure. *Post hoc* incorporation of bootstrapped intraindividual variability from *in vivo* BE studies to PBPK-simulated BE metrics seems to be a useful approach to assess the risks of failing to meet the BE criteria (11). However, *in vivo* data is not always available. Babiskin & Zhang assumed an intraindividual variability coefficient of 10% to the majority of system-related parameters and carried out thousands of VBE trials using different sample sizes whose results were used to estimate the probability of passing the regulatory BE criteria (55). Nevertheless, without knowing which systems parameters contribute most to the observed variability in exposure and how much they contribute, further research is warranted to verify assumptions with experimental data and leverage available replicate *in vivo* BE studies to identify and quantify interoccasion variability in system parameters.

A retrospective cross-sectional survey in the BE database of the US FDA revealed that high intraindividual variability due to drug substance pharmacokinetic characteristics accounted for 60% of the highly variable drugs (56). Furthermore, the majority of the highly variable drugs belong to Biopharmaceutics Classification System class II (poor solubility but high intestinal permeability) or IV (poor solubility and intestinal permeability), reinforcing the key role of drug solubility as a determinant of intraindividual variability in systemic drug exposure (57). Therefore, changes in the gastrointestinal milieu between occasions contribute to the intraindividual variability in systemic drug exposure. Nevertheless, a consensus has been recently reached among biopharmaceutical scientists that current PBPK models fail to capture intraindividual variability in gastrointestinal motility. It was recognized that further research is necessary to move from empirical or semi-empirical hydrodynamic models to fully mechanistic ones. Furthermore, the current dissolution models found in PBPK tools are based on adaptations of the Nernst-Brunner equation using high luminal volumes and a well-stirred environment, which is in contradiction with magnetic resonance imaging showing multiple pockets of water distributed in the gastrointestinal tract (58).

Extensive first pass metabolism is also a major contributor to high intraindividual variability (56). However, the utilization of AUC to compare the bioavailability between the test (T) and reference (R) formulations at the same dose and experimental design assumes that clearance (CL) does not change within the same individuals for a crossover design (*i.e.*, $CL_T = CL_R$):

$$\frac{F_T}{F_R} = \frac{\frac{AUC_T * CL_T}{dose_T}}{\frac{AUC_R * CL_R}{dose_R}} = \frac{AUC_T * CL_T}{AUC_R * CL_R} = \frac{AUC_T}{AUC_R}$$

where F_T and F_R are the systemic fractions for T and R formulations, respectively, and AUC is the area under the systemic concentration-time curve.

This assumption can be tested by comparing the elimination rate constant estimated in different occasions. In fact, empirical approaches using terminal-phase rate constant to correct AUC have been suggested to incorporate intraindividual variability in relative bioavailability studies (59-61). Complementarily, it was demonstrated that intraindividual variability was high for drugs metabolized by CYP3A4 (62). Therefore, modeling replicated crossover BE studies for different substrates of CYP3A4 may be useful to characterize CL-mediated variability within the same individuals between different occasions. It is also worth mentioning that the terminal half-life can be used as an indicator of changes in CL when the terminal phase is governed by the rate of elimination rather than absorption. The terminal phase might reflect absorption kinetics in the case of extended release formulations or for the drugs which have rapid elimination compared to the rate of absorption. Moreover, since the elimination rate is the ratio of CL to volume of distribution, any inter-occasional variability of the volume of distribution may influence the use of terminal half-life as an indicator of the change in CL. However, within subject variability in volume of distribution is generally known to be much less than variation in clearance within the same individual (16), thus the elimination rate constant or half-life in different occasions can be used to verify whether CL is the same within the same individual.

3. Research call to close scientific gaps

Each year, FDA consults with industry and the public to develop a list of regulatory science initiatives on generic drugs in accordance with the Generic Drug User Fee Amendments (GDUFA) (63). In FY2020, GDUFA Science and Research Priorities encourage the following research topic “*Expand the scientific understanding of the role of excipients in generic drug products to support the expansion of the Biopharmaceutics Classification System (BCS) of Class III biowaivers to drug products with differences in formulations larger than currently recommended in FDA guidance*”. This calling for research efforts will not only involve the investigation on the impact of excipients on dissolution and permeation, but also encourage the development of PBPK modeling approaches to link these *in vitro* characteristics to *in vivo* BE simulation, *e.g.*, generating model integrated evidence for generic drug development and assessment (64).

As previously mentioned, the recently developed gut microphysiological systems may better mimic the physiological expression of metabolizing enzymes, uptake and efflux transporters in the gut (36-38, 65). Therefore, further studies using these microphysiological systems would help on investigating the intestinal permeability of BCS III drugs as well as the performance of drug delivery systems in a (patho)physiologically-relevant *in vitro* environment. In addition, better characterization of gastrointestinal (GI) transit of drug product and physiological conditions including gastric pH and motility of GI tract under fasting and fed condition, e.g., by using smart pill (66), could also increase confidence when using these parameters to establish the PBPK model for BCS III drugs.

One of the centerpieces to enable using model integrated evidence for generic drug approval is via conducting VBE studies using sufficiently verified and validated models. Characterizing PK parameters uncertainties, especially the interindividual and intraindividual variabilities, and incorporating them in PBPK models will allow simulations of crossover studies. However, it has been technically challenging to quantitatively describe these uncertainties from a bottom up approach and this area warrants more research. Integrating quantitative global sensitivity analysis methods to PBPK modeling may be a useful way to map out major sources of variability in systemic drug exposure. Most common approaches consider a conservative option of assigning the same level of intraindividual variability as the interindividual variability. However, even the latter is not well known in many cases. Recently, Al-Majdoub et al pointed out that mixed effect models, which separates the intraindividual and interindividual variabilities, have not been used in any of the studies assessing the physiological parameters input into PBPK platforms (23). Therefore, future studies combining the classical data analysis (top-down) with PBPK-*in vitro in vivo* extrapolation-linked models may pave the way to incorporate intraindividual variability to system-related parameters by modeling observed clinical data collected from replicated crossover BE studies.

Other research gaps related to BE of orally administered drugs have been discussed in the recent publications (67, 68). The research efforts on these topics would be valuable to support synergistic use of models and characterization at critical decision points during generic drug product development and review.

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